

EFFECTS OF SPECIMEN GEOMETRY ON THE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF A QUASI-ISOTROPIC GRAPHITE/EPOXY COMPOSITE

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Results are presented for investigations of the effects of: 1) specimen width on fatigue life; 2) batch-to-batch material variations; 3) specimen length on fatigue life, and, 4) notches on both static and fatigue life. Tests were conducted using parallel sided T300/934 graphite/epoxy coupons cured at 177°C. All tests were conducted at room temperature under constant amplitude loading at frequencies of 10 Hz in laboratory air. Loading in all cases was tension-tension. Two specimen widths, 22.2 mm and 76.2 mm, were evaluated. Static tensile properties were obtained for notched and unnotched specimens of both sizes. Fatigue tests were conducted at two stress levels giving lives ranging from 10^3 to 10^7 cycles. Data analysis was performed and compared using both the 3 parameter Weibull and the double exponential (Gumbel) distribution forms. Fatigue life was found to be significantly affected by specimen width and stress level. Fatigue life was found to vary between different batches of vendor supplied prepreg. Changes in specimen length had minor effects on fatigue life and scatter. Precycling of notched specimens below ultimate strength reduces the effect of notches on life, and the amount of precycling appears to influence the degree of notch acuity reduction.

INTRODUCTION

Obtaining valid design data from small coupon testing requires a greater understanding of the relationship of specimen geometry to test results and their correlation to larger structures. Applications of the rules developed over many years of metallic specimen testing may or may not be valid in fibrous composites. The objective of this investigation was to establish the validity of these specimen design assumptions for one material and layup. Extrapolation of these results to other materials or layups is without basis at this time.

In establishing a test program the question arises from an economic standpoint of how small can test specimens be made to obtain meaningful data in order to minimize material cost, fabrication time, and test machine capacity requirements. Examination of damage growth in composite specimens indicated that in wide (76.2 mm) specimens delamination occurred at the edges and propagated inward for about 19 mm and stopped, whereas in narrow (22.2 mm) specimens the delaminations progressed completely across the width. Likewise the failed specimens appeared different, suggesting a possible difference in failure mechanism. If so, then effects on fatigue life could be possible. This investigation was conducted to evaluate fatigue life and static strength differences between wide and narrow specimens, the effect of specimen length on fatigue life, the effects of notches on fatigue life, and notch size effects on static strength. This report summarizes test results to date on one material and layup, work is continuing on other materials.

COUPON FABRICATION

The material used in this program was Fiberite system HY-E-1034C (Thornel T300/Fiberite 934 Resin). Layup orientation was (0/45/90/-45/-45/90/45/0)₂. Three lots of 305 mm wide prepreg tape were used for fabrication of panels. Each panel consisted only of material from one lot. Resin content, volatile content, and flow of the prepreg batches were inspected for conformance to specified tolerances upon receipt. All prepreg materials were stored in sealed moisture-proof bags in refrigerators and were allowed to come to room temperature before unsealing bags to prevent water condensation on prepreg surfaces. Layup of laminates was performed in a semi-clean room with temperature controlled to $21 \pm 3^\circ\text{C}$. This reduced contamination with dust or foreign matter. Controlled temperature assured proper tack and drape of prepregs and prevented water condensation problems. Fiber orientation in a layup was accomplished by use of suitable templates to meet required angle tolerances. Laminates were fabricated in an autoclave using vacuum pressure augmented by autoclave pressure. Cured panels were nondestructively inspected by ultrasonic "C" scan procedure for voids, delaminations and other defects. During specimen machining samples were removed from the center of each panel to measure resin content and density.

Panels were fabricated of approximate dimensions 0.914 x 1.219 m. The test panels were cut into 2 subpanels, numbered and sectioned as shown in Fig. 1. Configuration of the 22.2 and 76.2 mm coupons is shown in Fig. 2. All coupons were machined dry. For all tests, coupons were fabricated and machined identically so that any scatter in test results could not be attributed to variations in coupon fabrication procedures.

Figure 1. Typical Panel Layout and Specimen Orientation

Figure 2. Specimen Geometry

TEST PROCEDURES AND DATA

STATIC TENSILE TEST PROCEDURES AND DATA

Static tensile tests were performed on twelve unnotched 22.2 mm wide specimens from four panels fabricated from one batch of material. These data are summarized in Table 1. A three parameter Weibull analysis gave a 50% probability of survival of 529 MN/m². Six 76.2 mm wide specimens were also statically failed in tension and are likewise summarized in Table 1. The 50% probability of survival for the wide specimens is 492 MN/m².

Twelve 76.2 mm wide specimens with a single central 12.7 mm diameter hole in each were loaded to tension failure. An extensometer was attached to the specimen edge above the hole. Typical values of strain to failure were 0.0042 microstrain and modulus values of 5.17 x 10⁴ MN/m². Additionally 3 groups of five 22.2 mm wide specimens per group were tested in tension with 1.57, 3.25, and 6.35 mm dia. center holes. A three parameter Weibull analysis of these notched data are presented in Table 2.

FATIGUE TEST PROCEDURES AND DATA

Fatigue testing was accomplished using closed-loop electro-hydraulic servo controlled testing machines of various capacities from 89 to 534 MN maximum allowable load. Each machine was equipped with a peak and valley load monitoring system which allowed continuous monitoring of the load signal maximum peak, maximum valley, and minimum peak and minimum valley such that load accuracy was maintained within ±1.0% of full-scale reading. Fatigue grips were of the friction bolt type with integral internal alignment fixtures. Coupon alignment was maintained within 0.076 mm in any direction.

Specimen Width (mm)	22.2	76.2
Panel Code	1NH	1NH
Sample Size - n	12	6
Fit	0.0031156	0.0011102
K - Shape Parameter	16.6950	8.8293
e - Scale Parameter	-0.24974	-0.09806
Mean (MN/m ²)	524	485
Std. Deviation (MN/m ²)	38.8	66
V - Scale Parameter	78.49	74.34
Stress (MN/m ²) at Probability of Survival of:		
0.999	357	234
0.99	410	304
0.95	453	366
0.90	473	397
0.80	495	432
0.50	529	492
0.10	569	563

Table 1. Three Parameter Weibull Analysis of Unnotched Static Test Data

Specimen Width (mm)	22.2	22.2	22.2	76.2	76.2 [△]	76.2	76.2
Hole Diameter (mm)	1.57	3.25	6.35	12.7	12.7	12.7	25.4
Panel Code	IPJ884B	IPJ884B	IPJ884B	1QD	1QD	1QD	INH 831B
Sample Size - n	5	5	5	12	12	12	3
Fit	0.0005	0.0004	0.0007	0.0009	0.0005	0.0009	0.72×10^{-12}
K - Shape Parameter	11.600	29.009	11.848	18.59	18.43	18.59	9.957
e - Scale Parameter	-34.27	-17.39	-24.22	-0.030	-0.022	-0.030	-0.002
v - Scale Parameter	5.85×10^4	4.47×10^4	3.81×10^4	---	40.15	---	3.11×10^3
Mean (MN/m ²)	386	303	252	225	269	225	203
Standard Deviation (MN/m ²)	40	13	26	15	18	15	25
Stress (MN/m ²) at Probability of Survival of:							
0.99	271	263	178	180	216	180	134
0.95	312	279	205	197	236	197	159
0.90	332	285	217	205	245	205	170
0.80	354	293	232	213	255	213	184
0.70	370	298	241	---	---	---	193
0.50	391	305	255	226	272	226	206
0.10	434	318	282	241	290	241	232

[△] Net area - all others gross area

Table 2. Three Parameter Weibull Analysis of Notched Static Tensile Data

Fatigue tests were conducted by first applying the calculated mean load and setting the variable amplitude (span) control to 50% of the desired value. Cyclic loading was then begun. One hundred or less cycles were applied as the variable load was increased to the target value. This eliminated any possibility of a first cycle load overshoot. High speed visicorder traces were made of each such start up. Peak and valley error detectors were then engaged. Any input load deviations beyond $\pm 1/2\%$ were detected by the peak and valley detectors which shut down varying load and returned it to the mean value.

Most fatigue tests were conducted in laboratory air (50 $\pm 10\%$ R.H.) at 21 $\pm 3^\circ\text{C}$ and at 7 to 10 Hz. Tests were conducted mainly at two stress levels, 290 and 324 MN/m², at a stress ratio of $R \cong 0.01$.

DATA ANALYSIS

These data were reduced and compared using primarily a 3-parameter Weibull analysis procedure [1]. Fatigue data were also reduced and compared using an interactive computing regression analysis routine of the Gumbel or double exponential distribution form [2,3]. A discussion in detail of these two methods is presented by Bowie, et al [4] as applied to composite fatigue analysis, however briefly these two are summarized as follows:

• Weibull Three Parameter

$$P(x) = \exp \left[- \left(\frac{x-e}{v-e} \right)^k \right] \quad (1)$$

• Double Exponential (Gumbel)

$$P(x) = 1 - \text{Exp} \{ \text{Exp} [-\alpha(x-u)] \} \quad (2)$$

where

$P(x)$ = probability of survival
 x = fatigue life
 $k, e,$ and v are Weibull parameters
 α and u are double exponential function parameters

In all tables k, e, v, α and u as listed are calculated from English units.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

LENGTH EFFECTS

To explore possible changes in fatigue life due to test specimen length, three groups of 22.2 mm wide specimens were made with gage lengths of 22.2, 127 and 381 mm, giving length-to-width ratios of 1:1, 5.7:1, and 17:1.

Results of these tests are presented in Fig. 3 and Table 3. In general, within the length-to-width range tested decreasing specimen length produced higher mean life and increased scatter. This is as suspected since as length is increased the probability of a "weak-link" in the gage length increases. These results may be valid only for this particular quasi-isotropic layup and material, others must be likewise evaluated before specimen length-to-width design standards are established. A second width (76.2 mm) series is currently being tested. Based on these tentative results, the metallic specimen guidelines of length-to-width ratios of 2-1/2:1 to 3:1 appear reasonable.

Figure 3. Effects of Specimen Length on Fatigue Life

Length/Width	17/1	5.7/1	1/1
Stress (MN/m ²)	290	290	290
Panel Code	IPJ888A	IPJ888A	IPJ888AD
Sample Size - n	5	9	7
Fit	0.0683	0.0228	0.0845
K - Shape Parameter	1.968	1.980	2.817
e - Scale Parameter	-1.48 x 10 ⁵	-1.40 x 10 ⁵	-1.79 x 10 ⁶
v - Scale Parameter	1.03 x 10 ⁶	1.26 x 10 ⁶	5.64 x 10 ⁵
Mean	8.92 x 10 ⁵	1.10 x 10 ⁶	4.83 x 10 ⁶ + Δ
Standard Deviation	5.17 x 10 ⁴	6.53 x 10 ⁵	2.55 x 10 ⁶ +
Cycles to Failure at Percent Probability of Survival:			
99	-3.49 x 10 ⁴	-2.91 x 10 ⁴	-3.40 x 10 ⁵
95	1.11 x 10 ⁵	1.72 x 10 ⁵	7.98 x 10 ⁵ +
90	2.26 x 10 ⁵	3.09 x 10 ⁵	1.55 x 10 ⁶ +
80	3.99 x 10 ⁵	5.15 x 10 ⁵	2.57 x 10 ⁶ +
70	5.47 x 10 ⁵	6.91 x 10 ⁵	3.36 x 10 ⁶ +
50	8.26 x 10 ⁵	1.02 x 10 ⁶	4.74 x 10 ⁶ +
10	1.64 x 10 ⁶	1.99 x 10 ⁶	8.21 x 10 ⁶ +
Δ One specimen did not fail after 10 ⁷ cycles. Computations were made as if it were a failure at 10 ⁷ cycles, therefore actual values would be higher.			

Table 3. Three Parameter Weibull Analysis of Length Effects Fatigue Test Data

NOTCH EFFECTS ON STATIC STRENGTH

Static tensile tests were conducted on center notched 22.2- and 76.2-mm wide specimens as listed in Table 2. Specimens were loaded in a hydraulic grip and monotonically loaded to failure. Results of these tests were analyzed with the point stress criterion^[5] and are presented in Fig. 4. Correlation of the experimental data with the theoretical prediction is good for the 25.4- and 12.7-mm diameter holes, but diverges for smaller holes. Experimental results indicate a greater strength reduction for the small holes than predicted by this analytical method.

FATIGUE TEST RESULTS

Statistical analysis of all fatigue results was performed using two distributions. Results for the Weibull method are shown in Table 4, and for the Gumbel method in Table 5. Fig. 5 compares percent survivability results for both methods.

WIDTH EFFECTS

Fig. 6 graphically shows the difference between panel 1NH 22.2- and 76.2-mm wide specimen fatigue lives and their relative scatter. Statistical analyses performed with the Gumbel distribution show that at 324 MN/m² the narrow (22.2 mm) specimens have longer lives (7.3×10^5 cycles) by over a factor of two at the 50% probability of survival points or median points compared to the wide (76.2 mm) specimen (2.8×10^5 cycles). These comparisons are plotted at various probabilities

Figure 4. Effect of Notches on Static Strength

Specimen Width (mm)	76.2	76.2	76.2	22.2	22.2
Panel Code	1NH	1PJ	1NH	1NH	1NH
Type Specimen	Unnotched	Unnotched	Unnotched	Unnotched	Unnotched
Sample Size - n	17	12	9	20	8
Stress - MN/m ²	324	324	290	324	290
Fit	0.11415	0.40392	0.13095	9.69	0.03813
K - Shape Parameter	1.3965	0.5758	4.859	0.4958	2.2149
e - Scale Parameter	-7.79 x 10 ⁴	1400	-1.6 x 10 ⁶	4.22 x 10 ⁵	-8515
v - Scale Parameter	3.44 x 10 ⁵	7.83 x 10 ⁴	3.74 x 10 ⁶	6.27 x 10 ⁵	4.32 x 10 ⁶
Mean	3.07 x 10 ⁵	-	3.29 x 10 ⁶	-	3.82 x 10 ⁶
Standard Deviation	2.79 x 10 ⁵	-	1.15 x 10 ⁶	-	1.83 x 10 ⁶
Cycles to Failure at Percent Probability of Survival of:					
99.9	- *	1400	-	**	1.83 x 10 ⁵
99.0	-	1426	4.69 x 10 ⁵	-	5.33 x 10 ⁵
95.0	-	1842	1.30 x 10 ⁶	-	1.12 x 10 ⁶
90.0	6.32 x 10 ³	2944	1.76 x 10 ⁶	-	1.56 x 10 ⁶
80.0	6.63 x 10 ⁴	7086	2.32 x 10 ⁶	-	2.19 x 10 ⁶
50.0	2.47 x 10 ⁵	4.2 x 10 ⁴	3.35 x 10 ⁶	-	3.66 x 10 ⁶
10.0	6.89 x 10 ⁵	3.29 x 10 ⁵	4.74 x 10 ⁶	-	6.29 x 10 ⁶

* The fitted distribution curve predicts no life at this percent probability of survival.

** No cycles are predicted here because the data cannot be handled with a 3-parameter Weibull function since e is larger than the shortest life x

Table 4. Three Parameter Weibull Analysis of Fatigue Test Data

Specimen Width (mm)	76.2	76.2	76.2	22.2	22.2
Panel Code	1NH	1PJ	1NH	1NH	1NH
Sample Size - n	17	12	9	20	8
Stress (MN/m ²)	324	324	290	324	290
α - Shape Parameter	3.90×10^{-6}	5.20×10^{-6}	5.94×10^{-7}	1.84×10^{-6}	3.57×10^{-7}
u - Shift Parameter	1.86×10^5	3.45×10^4	2.50×10^6	5.33×10^5	3.17×10^6
Correlation Coefficient - r_0	0.984	0.914	0.852	0.9023	0.9541
Standard Deviation - σ	0.198	0.436	0.552	0.4829	0.3127
Sum of Squared Deviation - D^2	0.588	1.905	2.132	4.197	0.5867
Cycles to Failure at Percent Probability of Survival of:					
50	2.80×10^5	1.05×10^5	3.11×10^6	7.32×10^5	4.19×10^6
60	2.08×10^5	5.13×10^4	2.65×10^6	5.81×10^5	3.41×10^6
70	1.39×10^5	- *	2.19×10^6	4.32×10^5	2.64×10^6
80	6.41×10^4	-	1.70×10^6	2.74×10^5	1.83×10^6
85	2.20×10^4	-	1.42×10^6	1.85×10^5	1.37×10^6
90	-	-	1.10×10^6	0.80×10^5	0.82×10^6
95	-	-	6.52×10^5	-	9.02×10^4

*The fitted distribution curve predicts no life at this percent probability of survival.

Table 5. Gumbel Analysis of Fatigue Test Data

Figure 5. Comparison of Three Parameter Weibull and Gumbel Percent of Survivability Results

Figure 6. Effects of Specimen Width on Fatigue Life Test Conducted on Panel Series 1NH at 7 - 10 Hz in Laboratory Air and at $R \cong 0.01$

of survival in Fig. 5 for all specimen sizes, stress levels, and material batches. A comparison of the 324 MN/m² data is not made for the Weibull function since the k parameter is 0.4958. According to Olvston^[1] a value of $k < 1$ implies the test specimen material develops resistance to fatigue as the number of load cycles is increased. On this basis it does not appear that a Weibull function describes this data set. Likewise the 1PJ data group at 324 MN/m² does not yield valid Weibull predictions since $k = 0.5758$. Calculated values are plotted in Fig. 5 and tabulated in Table 4 for comparison with Gumbel analysis.

This life variation with width for 1NH panel specimens at 324 MN/m² is not as apparent at 290 MN/m². The 50% survivability points for 22.2 mm specimens and 76.2 mm specimens are 3.66×10^6 and 3.35×10^6 cycles respectively for the Weibull method and 4.19×10^6 and 3.11×10^6 cycles respectively for the Gumbel method. More significant, however, is the scatterband or dispersion between the two width groups, with the wide specimens having lives ranging over three orders of magnitude and the narrow specimens only one order of magnitude. This data analyzed from a design standpoint of say 85% probability of survival yields a factor of seven difference in life, 22,000 cycles for wide specimens versus 185,000 cycles to failure for narrow specimens at the 324 MN/m² level by the Gumbel method. As seen in Table 5 no comparisons can be made at probabilities of survival higher than 85% because the life prediction goes to zero at less than 90% even with 17 data points per condition when scatter of this type is encountered. As seen in Fig. 5 the Weibull method yields predictions that are less conservative than the Gumbel method.

PANEL-TO-PANEL VARIATIONS

Tests were conducted on specimens fabricated from a second set of panels, (code 1PJ) fabricated four months later than the 1 NH and 1 QD panels under identical procedures but from a different batch of prepreg. Results of these tests are presented in Tables 4 and 5. Fig. 7 compares the two sets of S/N data with Weibull probability of survival curves. At a stress of 324 MN/m² for 76.2 mm specimens, for a 50% probability of survival, the 1NH specimens have lives of 2.47×10^5 cycles versus 4.2×10^4 for the 1PJ series (Weibull distribution). Fig. 5 compares the data sets in both Weibull and Gumbel formats in more detail for analysis of dispersion. The Weibull shape parameter k for this data set is 0.5758 (Table 4). On this basis it does not appear that a Weibull function describes this data set. Even with the Gumbel analysis (Table 5) probability of survival estimates above 60% cannot be made with any confidence. The difference between the two groups of material and what mechanisms are responsible for their varying behavior have yet to be identified. A larger number of specimens, say 20 instead of the 12 tested, would probably more accurately define the life distribution function thus aid in better predictive analysis, but sufficient numbers of coupons are not available for further work.

Figure 7. Fatigue Life Differences Between Two Batches of Prepreg. Probability of Survival Percentages Based on Three-Parameter Weibull Analysis. Test Conditions were the same for both groups.

WIDE FATIGUE SPECIMEN EXAMINATION

Examination of wide specimen failures revealed basically two types of failures, one exhibiting a more brittle localized tensile type fracture, and one of considerable damage over a large area with much brooming. The first type occurred in specimens failing in less than 100,000 cycles and the second over 400,000 cycles. Those in between 100,000 and 400,000 cycles were a mixed mode partly of each type.

Narrow specimens were observed to start delaminating at the machined edges between the two -45° layers and progress inward until completely through the width. This normally did not occur until at least 50% of the failure life. After this outer layers delaminated in a similar manner until, near failure, few layers remained together. In the wide specimens similar initiation was noted but the delaminations never progressed more than 19 mm into the width from each edge. Multiple layer delamination occurred on some specimens but at failure had not propagated more than 19 mm inward. Localized buckling was noted on the wide specimens after approximately 75% of the fatigue life, as these areas produced an audible "oil canning" mode sound. Some areas 6 mm wide by 25 mm long would break free in the longitudinal direction from the surrounding surface and bow outward ~3 mm on each minimum load excursion. This was particularly interesting since the minimum load applied to the specimen was never less than 890 N, indicating panel residual stresses vary ply-by-ply. Such areas would greatly increase the susceptibility to environmental damage. Ultrasonic C scans made of all panels prior to specimen fabrication were inspected to see if any indications could be found which might explain these debond areas. Each specimens location and orientation was known precisely on the C scan record so that each debond area could be pinpointed but no correlation could be found.

The implications of the results to date indicate that by establishing design stresses based on small coupon data may give unconservative values for full scale structural applications. Full scale ground test articles are more important than ever to assure safe life.

NOTCH EFFECTS

In addition to the notched static tension tests a series of tension-tension fatigue tests were run using 76.2 mm wide specimens with a central 12.7 mm diameter hole in each. All of these tests were conducted at 7 Hz in lab air at a stress ratio of $R \approx 0.02$. These data are presented in Fig. 8.

Initial fatigue tests were begun at 75% (207 MN/m²) of the 50% probability of survival level of the static data (271 MN/m²). No failure occurred after approximately 5.3×10^6 cycles as shown by point A on Fig. 8. The stress was then increased to 234 MN/m² and the same specimen was subjected to an additional 3.5×10^6 cycles (point B) with no failure. The stress was increased again on that specimen and an additional 836,000 cycles applied at 276 MN/m² with no failure (point C). Finally the stress was increased to 324 MN/m² and an additional 32,000 cycles were applied before the specimen failed (point D). The probability of survival at this stress level for static failure is approximately 1×10^{-8} . Tests were repeated at different stress levels and the results of improved life far beyond normal static strength were confirmed. A series of tests were run at 241 MN/m² for 100,000, 200,000, 500,000, and 1,000,000 cycles with no failures. These were then rerun at 324 MN/m² to see what effect this precycling at a lower load (90% of the 50% probability of survival stress) had on fatigue life. As shown in Fig. 8 the greater the number of cycles applied at the lower stress the longer the life at the higher stress level. In other words, precycling below the static ultimate strength for several hundred thousand cycles effectively reduced the "notch acuity" of the hole. The mechanism of blunting or stress redistribution at the hole has not been explored at this point. Examination of the specimens during test show delaminations around the hole developing in the axis of loading, not at the maximum stress concentration area as shown in Fig. 9.

Figure 8. Fatigue Test Results of 12.7 mm Diameter Center Notched 72.2 mm Wide Specimens. Specimens Tested at Low Stress Levels with No Failure ($\circ \rightarrow$) were rerun at Higher Stress Levels. Tests were conducted at 7 Hz and $R \cong 0.02$

Figure 9. Delamination Growth in Center Notched Fatigue Specimens

This delamination type is then followed by splitting of the 0° surface fibers which continue propagating the full length of the specimen. The load transfer around the hole is shifted totally to the $\pm 45^\circ$ fibers and with the elliptical delamination area shown in Fig. 9, the notch radius R_1 in the 90° direction is effectively increased to R_2 , thus reducing the stress concentration.

CONCLUSIONS

The following conclusions may be drawn for the T300/934 graphite/epoxy material and layup tested in this program:

1. Fatigue life is affected by specimen width.
2. Wide specimens at high stress levels have lower fatigue strength than narrow specimens.
3. Wide specimens at high stress levels have much larger scatter than narrow specimens.
4. Predicting probability of survival beyond 95% for wide panels required a sample size beyond 15.
5. Significant fatigue strength variations occur between different vendor supplied prepreg batches.
6. Precycling of notched specimens below ultimate strength reduces the effect of the notch on life. The amount of precycling appears to influence the degree of notch acuity reduction.
7. Decreasing specimen length produces higher mean life and increased scatter over the length-to-width range from 1:1 to 17:1.

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